

IMPACT OF INCREASING SOCIAL ACTIVITY IN STUDENT GIRLS ON PROFESSIONAL SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the role of increasing social activity in schoolgirls in professional qualifications, the formation of professional skills and abilities, and the development of the psychological nature of professional inclinations.

INTRODUCTION. Due to the honor of national independence, attention to the education of the young generation has increased. One of the important components of the education of the perfect generation is the level of modern development of any society and its future, which can manifest its identity with its internal capabilities, creative initiative potential, and its acceptance and recognition by the society. It is the development of people who can prove themselves, who can be the real subject of their own destiny, who have the ability to search and create. It is known that any society strives to be humane in relation to its members, and its goal is the self-expression of a person, self-affirmation, recognition by society as a person. is to open the way to the realization of the need for recognition. Today, the political, economic and social changes taking place all over the world have brought about many changes in the theory and practice of education and training. Existing pedagogical practice in new social conditions cannot be implemented without a deep theoretical understanding of methodological and practical problems, because without solving these problems, it is impossible to achieve effectiveness in education and training.

METHODS. Descriptive method which presents all the collected information; Qualitative method which analyzes non-numerical data; Compare-and-contrast method which helps to figure out the differences and similarities between 2 objects of research: English and Uzbek teacher competences.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. Personal education, its social and psychological maturity is one of the main strategic issues of any country. Because it is impossible to build a society capable of achieving perfection in all aspects without educating a person on the basis of certain noble ideas and intellectual requirements. After all, in this process, first of all, the educational system, its content, and at the same time the psychological principles that serve to improve the educational system are important. Therefore, the fact that the issues of education of the perfect generation and its excellent education are being resolved at the level of state

policy is a sign that serious attention is being paid to the bright future of our youth, no less than anyone else.

It should be said that today in all educational institutions of our Republic, special attention is paid to the personality of the student and the future related to his socio-economic development. It is important to study, analyze and draw appropriate scientific and practical conclusions based on these. In addition, the formation of the student's attitude to the educational process is, first of all, to respect his individuality and uniqueness, to accept his talents, skills and capabilities as they are, naturally, and on this basis, to develop requires the creation of specific social and psychological conditions. In order to successfully implement this task, it is necessary to conduct pedagogical-psychological, especially social-psychological researches and implement appropriate measures based on their empirical results. At present, the acquisition of ready-made knowledge is not the main goal, but the most important thing is to develop the intellectual abilities of students and young people, to improve their professional interests, and to create their independent choice and decision-making skills.

The most important and common characteristic of a person who maintains a constant relationship with society, is self-aware, and coordinates his every action is his activity. Activity (a concept derived from the Latin "actus" - action, "activus" - active) is a category that explains how a person manifests all his actions in life. It explains everything we do, from the simple act of picking up a pencil in our hand and drawing a line, to the more complex actions we perform in our creative awakening moments. Therefore, in psychology, the problems of a person, his consciousness and self-awareness are described through the related qualities of his activity, participation in one or another type of activity, and his achievement. In any situation, all actions are controlled by the mind, both from the point of view of internal-psychological and external-consistency. Any activity includes both mental and physical - motor actions. For example, have you ever observed a wise man thinking? If you carefully observe a thinking person, although the leading activity in him is mental, his forehead, eyes, even body and hand movements are very important and serious, because he cannot stop thinking about something, or finding a new idea and taking it from him. Shows that he is happy. At first glance, the actions of a gardener who performs external elementary work - for example, ridding a grape seedling of excess leaves, are also not free of mental components.

Human activity is closely related to the concepts of action, activity, and behavior and goes back to the question of the individual and his consciousness. A person is formed in the process of various activities and shows his identity. Therefore, activity or human activity is not a passive process, but an active process that is consciously controlled. The process of actions embodying human activity is called activity. That is, activity is a specific form of activity controlled by the human mind and thinking, arising from various needs in it and aimed at changing and improving the external world and oneself. This is a game activity aimed at a young child to know the essence of real objects within his imagination, this is a labor activity aimed at creating material goods, this is a scientific research activity aimed at opening new discoveries, this is an athlete's skill aimed at increasing records. and the like. It is characteristic that a person is engaged in some kind of activity every minute. Social activism influences people's thoughts, feelings and actions in a certain sphere of social reality, evaluates the life of society and changes relevant aspects of social reality on this basis. Based

on the above considerations, it can be said that "social activity" is a criterion that indicates the level of awareness and perfection of a person in every field. Living in pursuit of social activity is an idea in itself. Its content consists of knowledge, manners, talents, abilities, positive skills and qualifications that ensure the spiritual growth of society, and a set of worldviews formed on the basis of these. Or, to be more precise, social activism consists of a set of ideas that lead a person's spirituality to maturity, embody all positive qualities, and serve to ensure social progress. The social activity of a future teacher-student is a quality of personality and a legal expression of ideological, political, professional-cultural and civil responsibility for the development of society. In addition to acquiring scientific knowledge of his subject, every future teacher must understand the content of the reforms implemented in our society, the changes taking place in the country, and be ideologically armed.

Today the educational system of all the European countries is on the way of transition to the competence model of development. In order to understand the overall competence educational scheme it is very important to examine and analyze European experience in this sphere.

"Competence" or "competency" is: 1) the ability to do something well; 2) a skill needed to do a particular job; 3) a standardized requirement for an individual to properly perform a specific job (after Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English).

But in spite of the existence of great number of scientific works, articles, documents belonging to the problem of the competence approach in the system of teachers' education in European countries, today there is no single unified classification of professional competences, essential for secondary school teachers to fulfill their professional functions successfully.

It was considered that European teachers' professional competences should include such components as:

1. European identity. European teacher is conscious with his own national roots and general union of European peoples. Teacher's values make it possible for him to teach not only in frameworks of the national programmes but far out of their limits. The key aspect of European identity is teacher's readiness to accept the differences and to treat the whole world with respect.
2. European knowledge which comprises teacher's outlook of educational systems peculiarities in different countries. Teachers respect their national educational system and correlate its quality with others. They know features of current world policy, history or regional countries and its influence on modern European development.
3. European multiculturalism. European teacher treats his national culture with respect and is ready to accept other cultures. He behaves confidently without domination over other cultures. He works in heterogeneous groups, respects differences and gives his pupils equal opportunities.
4. European language competence. European teacher knows more than one European language. Language skills he acquires in the system of life-long pedagogical education. It would be very important for him to spend some period in foreign environment to communicate with authentic language speakers.

5. European professionalism. European teacher has got his education due to which he can teach in every European country. He has “European” approach to the process of teaching of his specialised subject which helps him to treat educational material from the point of view of European perspective. He cooperates with European colleagues and takes the best pedagogical traditions. Modern practice of common teacher training programmes and confirmation of unified scientific Degrees in European universities helps to develop European level of professionalism.

6. European citizenship. European teacher must work and live as the citizen of Europe accepting such values as people rights respect, democracy, freedom. His critical style of teaching should form autonomous, active citizens of Europe.

7. European quality measuring. European teacher training foresees the existing of instruments for comparison of regional countries educational systems formal features. Means of comparability and transparency development, worked out in Bologna and Copenhagen, influenced the process of obstacles elimination in the acceptance of pedagogical qualifications and in increase of teachers mobility.

8. European teachers mobility comprises possibilities of studying abroad, learning of foreign languages, getting acquainted with different national cultures, taking part in exchange programmes of students within the EU, individual job placement abroad. European teacher develops his pupils’ mobility too. Pupils exchange programmes within EU give additional opportunities for education and new understanding of European citizenship.

Analysis of European documents made it possible to formulate the model of a professionally competent European teacher. This model is represented on the scheme 1. Judging from the scheme professional competences of European teachers may be divided into the following groups: **key competences; basic competences; specialised or subject competences.**

Key competences are necessary for performance of any professional activity. Thanks to them an individual feels comfortable in social and professional environment, solving professional tasks due to the correct use of information, communication, social and legislative norms existing in the society.

Key competences of teachers should include: 1) information-communicative competence: the ability of a teacher to look for, analyze and select the necessary information; the knowledge of information technologies, computer programming including communication through INTERNET; 2) social-labour competence: the ability to take the responsibility; the ability to combine personal interests with the social needs; willingness for independent professional decisions; 3) language competence: the ability for oral and written communication in different languages; teacher’s talent to inform his pupils clearly and obviously from the point of view of both the depth of subject context and the way of teaching; moreover modern teachers must carry out the information in such a way as to make the pupils to continue their work independently; 4) values of an individual: realization of a teacher’s role and destination in the modern society, in European and world environment; necessity and ability to self-perception; active life viewpoint; promoting of values of a democratic society and their use in everyday life and professional activities; 5) cultural

competence: profound knowledge of national, European and world culture; tolerant attitude to different ethnic cultures.

Basic competences show the specific character of teaching profession. Basic competences for pedagogical activities are based on the abilities, knowledge and skills of the European teacher of the XXI century. They include: *Organizational competence*- the ability of a teacher to organize pupils effectively, to manage and control their educational activities and to plan and correct teacher's own activity.

Didactical competence - the ability of a teacher to transmit knowledge to the pupils in the way that makes them interested in the learning subject so that they are ready to continue their cognitive activity independently by themselves. European didactically competent teacher can easily adapt or reconstruct teaching material taking into account mental, social, cultural and ethnic differences of his pupils using various methods and forms of personally-oriented teaching.

Pedagogical thinking - the specific reflexive capability of a teacher to realize his own personality in pedagogical reality, to foresee the results of his activity and to plan the pupil's future educational trajectory. This ability in Ukrainian context is connected with positive and optimistic attitude to life and belief in people.

Cognitive-creative competence - the ability of a teacher to learn through understanding of what is necessary for a pupil. This competence is important when teachers formulate the aims of teaching process, plan and analyze cognitive activities of both his students and his own using creative skills.

Psychological competence - determination of a child individual as the dominant of education. Modern teacher must be psychologically ready to accept the inner life of a child, to understand his unique personality, to feel pupil's psychological difficulties and when it is necessary to give psychological help for a child.

Evaluative competence - the ability of a teacher to examine objectively the results of pupils achievements, the effectiveness of his own work and the professional work of his colleagues, positive and negative features in the system of education as a whole.

Consultative competence - the ability of a teacher to provide consultations and different forms of psychological-pedagogical assistance in the process of construction of pupil's educational path.

Competence of lifelong development - the teacher's talent to evolve his professional skills, knowledge and competences during all his life.

Special competences demonstrate the level of subject component in teaching profession. They are considered by European scientists as abilities of a teacher to realize his basic and key competences in the process of teaching major subjects at school. Special competences include two components: 1) subject competence; 2) research competence.

In the process of formation of special competences the academic capabilities (**subject competence**) of teachers play a very important role. A teacher must have the ability to master and renew his knowledge of the subject he teaches at school.

CONCLUSION. Vocational education for a long time was aimed at educating a comprehensively developed person, but this process was carried out at the expense of a decrease in the level of formation of professional skills of graduates. This situation did not

serve to increase the need to improve professional skills and abilities, to improve one's knowledge and self-education throughout one's life. As a result of the reforms in the education system of our republic, special attention is being paid to the issue of vocational training for working professions, the formation of professional skills and abilities in the learner.

In short, the formation of social activity of young people and the analysis of the psychological essence of professional inclination allowed us to put forward the following scientific hypothesis:

- Increasing the activity of young people in the formation of their socialization process by activating various forms of subjectivity specific to them and creating conditions for the development of personality traits provides an opportunity to increase their professional knowledge.;
- Increasing the activity of young people, creating conditions for understanding alternatives in the form of cooperative relations (the need to choose one of the two possible opposites) in the formation of their socialization process can be the subject of the activity of a school psychologist.;
- It is likely that the activity of increasing the activity of young people in mutual cooperation will serve as a condition for self-development in order to overcome obstacles in the formation of their professional interests.

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